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RESULTS OF THE APPLICATION OF COSMETICS ON THE MODEL OF FIBROBLAST CELL CULTURE

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Abstract

The article describes the data of cosmetic agents' effect on the proliferative activity of cell line of fibroblasts. In addition, their effects on cells under conditions of oxidative stress.

Keywords: the culture of human fibroblasts, proliferation, oxidative stress

Skin care products are constantly being improved; new properties of active cosmetic ingredients that help slow down the aging process of the skin are regularly revealed. However, the composition of many means is not perfect and requires correction.

The purpose of the study is to evaluate the effect of medium-priced cosmetics on cultured human fibroblasts.

Materials and methods

The studies were performed on human fibroblastic cells. The culture of dermal fibroblasts was obtained from the skin explant of the donor, on the basis of his written informed consent, according to the original method [1].

The cells were cultivated at 37 ° C, CO₂ concentration of 5% and humidity of 95% in DMEM / Ham F-12 with the addition of 10% fetal bovine serum in an incubator (Sanyo, Japan). Daily microscopic monitoring of the state of cell cultures was performed using an inverted microscope with the Olympus CKX 41 photo documentation system.

The study examined the effect of samples provided by Unilever Rus:

1. Cosmetic preparation No. 1, which includes a herbal combination of chamomile infusion, akebiia, clover extract, vitamins of groups C, E.

2. Cosmetic preparation No. 2, containing beta-glucan with extracts of golden root, chamomile, extracts of ginseng root.

3. The combination of solutions No. 1 and No. 2

Before starting work, the working concentration of the solutions was found. To determine the toxic and working concentrations used the method of serial dilutions.

In order to study the effect of the studied solutions and their combination on the proliferative activity of human skin fibroblasts, cells were sown in well plates. After 24 hours, the test samples were applied and incubated for 24 hours. On the next day, a complete change of culture medium was made and the first cell count was performed. The following calculations were carried out on days 2.3 and 4 [2].

The total number of cells was counted using an automatic Scepter 2.0 cell counter (USA).

The influence of hydrogen peroxide was used as a model of toxic stress. Preliminary experiments established that in vitro for human derma fibroblasts, the absolute cytotoxic effect was 25 nM / ml. In this regard, the range from 7.2-24.2 nM / ml was used as working concentrations. Various concentrations of hydrogen peroxide were introduced into the culture of the studied solutions, the experiment was carried out for 24 hours [2].

Viability assessment was performed by staining cells with a 0.4% trypan blue solution (Sigma, USA). Stained samples were examined using a light microscope in the Goryaev chamber, while cells were counted, calculating the percentage of non-viable cells from the total number of cells [2].

Statistical processing of the data was carried out using Excel. To assess the significance of differences between groups, the Mann-Whitney test was used. When the error probability was $p < 0.05$, the differences between the mean values were considered significant.

Results and discussion

From our data it follows that at the maximum concentration of solution No. 2 (1: 3200), the effect of

stimulation is expressed slightly. On the 1-2 day of cultivation, the effect of inhibition was observed (by 10-11% in relation to the control), by the 4th day there was an insignificant stimulation of cell growth (by 3% in relation to the control). A two-fold decrease in the concentration of the solution (1: 6400) was accompanied by the disappearance of the effect of inhibition at the beginning of day 1 and the acceleration of proliferation by the end of day 4 (by 13% relative to the control) (Fig. 1).

When introduced into the culture of solution No. 1 in the minimum dilution (1: 12800) for 1-2 days, the effect of inhibiting the proliferation of fibroblasts (8-11% relative to the control) and stimulation by the end of 4 days (10%) . A two-fold reduction in the applied

dose of the drug was accompanied by the complete leveling of cell growth inhibition and an acceleration of proliferation by the end of 4 days (Fig. 1).

The combination of solutions at the maximum concentration of 1: 12800 studied was accompanied by pronounced inhibition of proliferation (by 13% relative to the control) and pronounced stimulation by the end of the observation period (by 18.5%). A two-fold decrease in concentration resulted in leveling of the effect of inhibition on the first day and stimulation of cell proliferation by the last day of observation (by 17.5%) (Fig. 1).

Since there is an effect of inhibiting cell proliferation, it can be assumed that the preparations contain components that inhibit cell division. Therefore, the composition of drugs should be adjusted.

Fig. 1. Growth curves of human dermal fibroblasts under the influence of the studied solutions and their combination over time (in% relative to the control)

From the data obtained in determining the resistance of cells to oxidative stress, it follows that hydrogen peroxide at a concentration of less than 15 nM / ml does not affect the solutions under study. This may be due to the low sensitivity of cells to its damaging effect.

In the concentration range from 14.5-21.8 nM / ml, the highest protective effect was observed for a solution of 16.9 nM / ml and 2 times at a concentration of 19.4

nM / ml). A decrease in the concentration of the solution by two times was accompanied by a decrease in the protective action (Fig. 2).

In solution No. 2, the protective effect is less pronounced.

The effect of hydrogen peroxide on the combination of solutions was characterized by an intermediate effect.

Fig. 2. The proportion of non-viable fibroblasts when modeling oxidative stress

The data obtained indicate an increase in the proliferative activity of cells under the influence of solutions in certain concentrations, therefore, the addition of these solutions to the composition of cosmetic products will promote skin renewal. Increased mitotic activity may be due to the presence in the composition of solutions of substances that enhance the proliferative activity of fibroblasts. These may be activators of plant-derived telomerase, which increase the proliferative potential of cells, extending the average telomere length [4]. It can also be assumed that, under the influence of the studied solutions, there is an increase in the release of fibroblast growth factors, which contributes to in turn, intracellular signaling cascades of mitogen-activated protein kinases (mitogen-activated protein kinases, MAPK): ERK1 / 2, JNK, p38 and ERK5 are induced, of which the most significant are ERK1 / 2 [2]. These kinases are capable of inducing the synthesis of pyrimidines, remodeling chromatin, participating in the synthesis of new ribosomes, activating the translation and transcription factors, as well as regulating the G1 / S and G2 / M transitions between phases of the cell cycle.

Differences in the chemoprotective effect of solutions can be explained by differences in the composition of these solutions. Probably, in solution No. 1 or more natural antioxidants are presented, the complex of antioxidants with their synergists, which reduce the number of reactive oxygen species in the cell, protect lipids from peroxidation, help maintain cell integrity and resistance to adverse effects [2].

Conclusion

1. The investigated substances have the ability to activate the proliferation of skin cells.
2. The data obtained indicate a pronounced cytoprotective effect of solutions, which may be due to the presence of natural antioxidant substances in their composition.
3. It is possible that the substances contained in the solutions contribute to the activation of telomerase and the release of growth factors that increase the proliferative potential of the cells.
4. The studied solutions contain components (component) that have a negative effect on the positive effects identified. Significant in the future may require correction of their recipes.

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